

The questionnaire was originally developed, validated, and applied in Spanish. For clarity, table headings and notes have been translated into English; the original data remain in Spanish.

"Spearman's bivariate correlations (ρ)"

Pedagogical Practice Variables	Perception of Diversity Variables				Professional Training in UDL Variable	
	Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)	Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)	Language Disorder (LD)	Migrant students	Initial Training	Continuing Education
Rho de Spearman						
C1. I promote freedom of choice and autonomous work.	-.299 ,029	-.103 ,332	-.098 ,356	-.253* ,015	-.006 ,954	,036 ,738
C2. I provide various options to motivate learning, taking into account my students' creativity, identity, and interests.	-.146 ,169	-.158 ,135	-.266* ,011	-.108 ,308	,073 494	,123 ,245
C3. I encourage play and a respectful learning environment	-.005 ,962	,118 ,266	,052 ,627	,038 ,721	,052 ,622	,125 ,239
C4. I address biases and minimize threats and distractions in the classroom	,033 ,759	-.041 ,697	-.035 ,741	,006 ,957	,137 ,195	,070 ,511
C5. I maintain effort and consistency by modeling and scaffolding learning objectives, activities, and achievement indicators according to my students' characteristics.	,083 ,433	-.104 ,325	-.234* ,026	-.187 ,075	,107 ,311	,132 ,211
C6. I facilitate strategies or procedures to scaffold and optimize learning challenges.	-.013 ,902	-.053 ,615	-.057 ,594	-.151 ,153	,158 ,136	,101 ,343

C7. I promote peer collaboration and collective learning.	,192 ,069	,059 ,578	-,086 ,419	,042 ,692	,056 ,595	,156 ,140
C8. I foster a sense of belonging to the community.	-,004 ,970	,024 ,819	-,018 ,865	-,168 ,110	,070 ,511	,134 ,204
C9. I provide consistent and in-depth feedback on my students' performance using instruments based on measurable indicators.	-,008 ,942	-,135 ,202	-,166 ,116	-,232* ,027	,083 ,433	,112 ,290
C10. I identify my students' expectations, beliefs, and motivations.	-,015 ,885	,001 ,990	-,197 ,061	-,134 ,206	,178 ,092	,058 ,586
C11. I establish behavioral guidelines and conflict-resolution methods agreed upon with the group.	,012 ,908	-,172 ,102	-,312** ,003	-,312** ,003	,094 ,378	,128 ,228
C12. I promote strategies for emotional self-regulation and both group and individual reflection in students.	-,120 ,256	-,069 ,514	-,165 ,117	-,193 ,066	,277* ,008	,157 ,138
C13. I foster empathetic and meaningful interpersonal relationships with my students.	,100 ,348	-,049 ,646	-,185 ,079	-,254* ,015	,174 0,98	-,003 ,979
R14. I use the whiteboard and adapt the information in textbooks and written materials to facilitate perception and understanding.	-,115 ,277	-,021 ,840	-,141 ,182	-,200 ,057	,148 ,161	,118 ,264
R15. I design personalized and innovative learning experiences with the support of ICT, creating manipulable or interactive materials that facilitate students' perception of information.	-,143 ,176	,036 ,737	-,159 ,131	-,030 ,775	,102 ,335	,101 ,342
R16. The selected educational materials consider diverse perspectives, identities, and cultures.	-,002 ,987	,096 ,363	-,105 ,323	-,112 ,291	,029 ,786	,075 ,487
R17. I frequently clarify the vocabulary, symbols, and linguistic structure of the materials or instructional resources.	,053 ,615	-,018 ,864	-,168 ,112	-,115 ,279	,040 ,703	-,117 ,270
R18. I use additional educational resources to support the understanding of texts, mathematical notations, and symbols.	-,104 ,329	,109 ,302	-,085 ,422	-,212* ,043	,073 ,491	,087 ,411

R19. I promote understanding of and respect for languages and cultural differences.	,169 ,110	,064 ,549	,051 ,632	-,054 ,610	,090 ,396	,071 ,507
R20. I address biases in the use of language and symbols to ensure proper access to information.	-,015 ,888	,002 ,985	-,139 ,190	-,103 ,330	,057 ,591	,144 ,173
R21. I illustrate information in various media of representation according to the learning paces and styles of my students.	,002 ,984	,047 ,658	-,197 ,062	-,098 ,354	,208* ,048	,160 ,129
R22. I develop new knowledge by connecting it with my students' prior learning.	,009 ,933	-,023 ,831	-,021 ,842	-,156 ,139	,239* ,002	,057 ,590
R23. I illustrate patterns, characteristics, main ideas, and relationships within knowledge.	-,044 ,678	-,207* ,049	-,070 ,510	-,278** ,008	,144 ,175	,031 ,771
R24. I develop active methodologies that enable the assignment of new meanings to knowledge.	-,007 ,945	-,014 ,898	-,093 ,379	-,152 ,150	,292* ,005	,166 ,117
R25. I create challenging learning situations that enable students to apply and transfer information to other contexts.	-,028 ,793	,054 ,609	-,146 ,166	-,121 ,254	,196 ,062	,014 ,893
A26. I diversify assessment and interaction methods through concept maps, collaborative work, gamification, among others.	,056 ,600	,040 ,707	-,146 ,168	-,012 ,909	,067 ,526	,138 ,191
A27. I provide access to materials, technologies, and assistive tools to interact during learning.	,012 ,910	,153 ,148	-,038 ,719	-,116 ,273	,101 ,340	,138 ,191
A28. I establish diverse forms of expression and communication of learning, such as verbal, written, graphic, exams, debates, among others.	-,062 ,557	-,093 ,382	-,191 ,070	-,176 ,095	,126 ,236	,072 ,497
A29. I facilitate various tools for the construction of creative knowledge through platforms and interactive applications such as Canva or Kahoot, Project- or Problem-Based Learning, creative writing, and Art or design projects.	,028 ,790	,094 ,378	-,136 ,199	-,051 ,630	,143 ,177	,159 ,132

A30. I gradually develop students' skills through practical learning activities.	-,013 ,904	,010 ,924	-,158 ,135	-,074 ,488	,195 ,064	,051 ,630
A31. I addressed biases in the modes of expression and communication of learning.	-,036 ,738	,036 ,736	-,147 ,164	-,092 ,387	-,002 ,984	,052 ,624
A32. I establish meaningful objectives according to my students' interests and competencies.	,034 ,751	-,044 ,680	-,206 ,050	-,118 ,266	,110 ,300	,034 ,751
A33. I develop strategies to plan objectives and anticipate challenges.	-,011 ,916	-,164 ,121	-,199 ,059	-,279** ,007	,135 ,203	,085 ,426
A34. I organize information and resources to optimize learning	-,059 ,579	-,092 ,387	-,179 ,089	-,166 ,117	,210* ,046	,058 ,587
A35. I effectively monitor my students' learning progress	-,007 ,950	-,170 ,108	-,177 ,093	-,152 ,150	-,014 ,895	,109 ,303
A36. I reflect critically and inclusively on my teaching practices.	,074 ,489	-,046 ,667	-,205 ,052	-,220* ,036	,201 ,056	,158 ,135

Assigned Values for the Variables Used in the Correlations Training in UDL (DUA)

0. No training
1. Initial training
2. Continuing training
3. Self-taught

Continuing Training (Detailed Level)

0. No training
1. Course or workshop
2. Diploma program
3. Post–certificate program (Postítulo)
4. Graduate program (Postgraduate)